

THE TEACHING SYSTEM IN VALLEY MUSIC SCHOOLS AND ITS SPECIFIC FEATURES

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ABSTRACT

Taking into account that the educational process in music schools is organized in a specific manner, this article provides information about music education and the systems of group and individual instruction within it, the content of subject curricula, study plans, and the changes made to them. The impact of changes in the program structure on the educational process is analyzed.

Introduction

Considering that the prosperity of a nation depends on the strength of its spiritual values, it is of great importance to further improve attitudes toward culture and the arts and to continue providing social protection for this sector and those working within it under market economy conditions. In such circumstances, without state support for culture—particularly for musical art and education—the development of this art form would not be easy. With a deep understanding of this reality, the Government of Uzbekistan began comprehensive reforms of the spiritual and cultural spheres from the very first days of independence.

The Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted in recent years—namely, Decree No. PF-4947 of February 7, 2017, “On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan,” Decree No. PF-4956 of February 15, 2017, “On Measures to Further Improve the Management System in the Sphere of Culture and Sports,” Resolution No. PQ-3022 of May 31, 2017, “On Measures for the Further Development and Improvement of the Sphere of Culture and Art,” Resolution No. PQ-3325 of October 16, 2017, “On the Establishment of the Fund for the Development of Culture and Art,” and Resolution No. PQ-112 of February 2, 2022, “On Additional Measures for the Further Development of the Sphere of Culture and Art,” serve as vivid examples of these reforms.

Results and discussion

Among the changes that took place in music schools during the years of independence, reforms related to the areas of specialization and the teaching of subjects have been of particular importance. At the initial stage of their establishment, music schools offered 5–6 areas of study, mainly including piano, violin, cello, bayan–accordion, wind orchestra, and folk instruments classes. Across the republic, the majority of music school students were educated

in the piano specialization, while the folk instruments class existed only at the music school in the city of Fergana [1: 96].

In the early 1990s, the existing areas underwent changes in terms of content and were significantly enriched. For example, a number of instrumental specializations began to be classified as folk instruments. In addition, new areas such as traditional singing, traditional performance, visual arts, artistic design, theater, and choreography were introduced. The folk instruments specialization was first clearly systematized within higher music education in the 1950s. This area includes wind instruments (nay and its varieties, qo'shnay, surnay, bolaman), plucked and struck string instruments (chang, tanbur), plucked string instruments played with a plectrum or fingernails (rubob and its varieties, dutor, dutor-bass, oud), percussion instruments (doira, nog'ora, and percussion instruments used in symphonic orchestras), and bowed string instruments (g'ijjak and its varieties, bayan) [3: 56]. The instruments taught within the folk instruments specialization help to develop skills for performing traditional folk melodies.

The expansion of the range of specializations in music schools is associated with the enrichment of traditions in the music education process and the growing demand in accordance with the needs of the time. In the early years of independence, music schools in the Fergana, Andijan, and Namangan regions mainly provided instruction in eight areas: piano, folk instruments, percussion and wind instruments, bowed string instruments, choir, artistic design, choreography, and bayan–accordion.

At that time, the standard duration of study was generally seven years; however, in violin, piano, viola, and cello classes it was eight years, while in other specializations it was six years (currently five years) [2]. This change may be related to revisions in the admission age stipulated in the Regulations. After independence, efforts to promote the historical and national culture of the Uzbek people were also reflected in the process of reviving distinctive and gradually forgotten traditions within the country's musical culture. The establishment of such areas as traditional performance and applied arts in music schools contributed to the development of national music, while the introduction of theater, choreography, and visual arts facilitated integration with global music and art practices.

According to the state program adopted in 2008, the construction of schools in the regions [5: 168] and the subsequent merging of music and art schools led to a further increase in the number of specializations. For example, in 2015, 280 students were enrolled in folk instruments, piano, wind and percussion instruments, pop singing, traditional singing, choreography, visual arts, applied arts, and theater at Music and Art School No. 25 in Pakhtaobod District [6: 4]. At Music and Art School No. 1 in the city of Andijan, education was provided between 2008 and 2016 in piano, string instruments, folk instruments, wind and percussion instruments, pop performance, pop singing, visual arts, and choreography [4]. At present, music and art schools in the region offer education in 14 specializations. Among these, the youngest is the baxshichilik (epic storytelling) specialization, which was established in 2019.

During the years of independence, the teaching of subjects in music schools became one of the key issues on the educational agenda. The music school education system has several distinctive features, the most important of which is that lessons are conducted in both group

and individual formats. In music schools, areas of education are divided into music and arts tracks: the music track includes instruction in 10 subjects, while the arts track offers 8–10 subjects.

In the music track, classes are organized either individually or in groups depending on the subject. For example, in piano and string instrument programs with a seven-year duration, as well as in pop performance programs based on these instruments, in addition to the main specialization subject (Grades 1–7), the following subjects are taught: solfeggio (Grades 1–7); ensemble performance or general piano (for string instruments) (Grades 1–7); sight-reading (Grades 2–5); ensemble (Grades 3–7); maqom alphabet (Grade 3); accompaniment (Grades 5–7); foreign music literature (Grades 4–5); Uzbek music literature (Grades 6–7); and elective subjects (Grades 2–7). Among these, the specialization subject, ensemble, accompaniment, sight-reading, and elective subjects are taught individually, while the remaining subjects are conducted in group lessons.

In other music specializations with a five-year duration, along with the specialization subject, the above-mentioned disciplines are also taught. In the fields of academic singing, traditional singing, and pop singing, the subjects of voice training and acting skills are taught instead of ensemble and sight-reading. The subjects within the arts track have their own specific characteristics; in visual arts and applied arts specializations, classes are conducted according to nearly identical curricula.

In choreography, instruction includes specialization and elective subjects, Uzbek dance, rhythmic, folk stage dance, historical and social dance, modern dance, ballet, the history of Uzbek dance, music literacy, and music appreciation. In the theater arts track, along with specialization and elective subjects, students are taught stage speech, stage movement, the history of world art and theater, rhythmic and dance, vocal performance, and stage practice.

In the arts track, all subjects—except stage speech, vocal performance, and elective subjects—are conducted in group formats [11].

Changes in the curricula of music and art schools did not create major differences across the stages of school development. The main distinctions were not in the subjects themselves, but in the number of hours allocated to them. When the specialization of traditional instrumental performance was added to the music school curriculum, the subject “Voice Training,” which had been taught within this specialization, was removed from the 2019 curriculum. This change was explained by the priority given to developing performers’ skills in working primarily with their musical instruments, while shaping vocal abilities was considered an excessive additional workload. Among the newly introduced subjects, the most significant are “Maqom Alphabet” and “Fundamentals of Maqom and Shashmaqom.” These subjects were included in the curriculum in order to ensure the implementation of the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-3391, “On Measures for the Further Development of Uzbek National Maqom Art” [7: 99]. In particular, starting from 2020, the teaching of the subject “Maqom Alphabet” was introduced for Grade 3 students in seven-year music and art school programs and for Grade 1 students in five-year programs, with the aim of fostering students’ interest in maqom art and enabling them to understand its theoretical foundations [8]. Although the subject “Fundamentals of Maqom” had been taught as an academic discipline at the Uzbekistan State Conservatory since 1972, it was a new

subject for music schools. All other subjects have been consistently included in the curriculum since the establishment of the respective specializations. In addition, based on the above-mentioned Resolution, a Maqom boarding school was established on the basis of Music and Art School No. 4 in the city of Fergana [9]. This regional school—the only one of its kind in the Fergana Valley—provides talented youth selected from the Andijan, Namangan, and Fergana regions with in-depth training in maqom art under the guidance of highly qualified specialists. As a result of professionally delivered education, students of this school successfully participate in international and national competitions. Alongside this boarding school, specialists have also proposed integrating maqom art into music lessons in all schools to instill its values in the younger generation, which would represent another important step in the development of this field. In particular, developing a four-year program plan using accessible and engaging methods to convey the philosophy and history of this art form to students is considered timely and necessary [10]. Since not everyone can perform maqom equally, the development of maqom teaching programs requires a differentiated approach. If curricula for teaching maqom are implemented based on systematic exposure to national music, their effectiveness will be even greater. Today, a range of institutions contribute to the development of maqom art, whose cultural and aesthetic significance continues to grow. These include cultural centers, music schools, maqom schools, the National Maqom Art Center established in 2017, and the Yunus Rajabiy Uzbek National Institute of Musical Art established in 2020. This music serves not only as a form of traditional folk art but also as a unifying force that fosters national identity and spiritual values among the people.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be stated that during the years of independence, the range of specializations in music and art schools of the Fergana Valley regions has significantly expanded, and the variety of national Uzbek instruments within the folk instruments specialization has been broadened. As a result, educational institutions have evolved from simple music schools into comprehensive music and art schools. While there are no major issues with student enrollment in urban schools, rural schools face considerable challenges in filling admission quotas. To address these issues, efforts are currently underway to explore and implement new approaches.

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